

TRANSLATION PROBLEMS OF MEDICAL TERMS

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Annotation

In this article we analysed medical texts and translation problems of medical terms by transcription and transliteration way.

Key words: medical terms, transliteration, transcription, equivalent, sphere, translation, analyze.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada biz tibbiy matnlarni va tibbiy atamalarning tarjima muammolarini transkripsiya va transliteratsiya yo'li bilan tahlil qildik.

Kalit so'zlar: tibbiy atamalar, transliteratsiya, transkripsiya, ekvivalent, soha, tarjima, tahlil.

The translation of medical terms from English into Uzbek represents an interesting and rich area for translation studies. All European languages share the same Greco-Latin roots in medical terminology. The preservation of the Latin language as the language of sciences until the 19th century, contributed to a great range of lexical similarities in medical nomenclature, and its effects can be observed until today. The knowledge of the Latin roots helps professionals in the field of medicine understand medical texts in different languages. [1]

A work of a skilled translator is applied here. For he/she must be good at not only translating skills but also medical sphere as well as its history, development, and many other things. While translating the terms of some field, translator should take into consideration the cultural background of this or that language. It must be done in the way that is acceptable by nation. While concentrating on terms, it is worth to give some information about them in general. The terms are the words or

phrases which have a special and strictly defined meaning in the field of science. They must definitely express the sense, the processes and the names of the objects in any sphere of industry. The terms in medical in the sphere stomatology are not exception, too. In order to analyze the terms in the defined tools of translation and give their proper translation in English and Uzbek, we should, firstly, define the morphological structure of the words.

All terms in their structure we divided into three groups:

- simple – bone, pulp, gums, root, caries, cavity;
- compound – interproximal, intraoral, pedadontist, radiograph;
- phrases – cross contamination, decalcification, gingival hypertrophy, impacted tooth;

Simple words are found in the frame of only one system and are characterized as monosemantic and they can be as the key words of the given subject. Compound terms can be found in one system, but they have different meanings depending on the context. For example, the word intraoral has the meaning a mouth.

According to this it is necessary to look for such kind of terms in the thesaurus or explanatory dictionaries where the given word can be found. Phrasal terms introduce the chain of words. The main element of these terms is the last word, and the key one is the penultimate word, word combination or compound term. Because of the usual use such terms can be substituted by the abbreviations. For example, FBS - Fasting Blood Sugar, ECG - Electrocardiogram Among the main methods of translation of the stomatology means the following is observed: Method of semantic development is applied when a dictionary equivalency of a word does not coincide with the context. For example, the word which is commonly used in stomatology –root, it has several meanings in the dictionary: koct – suyak (milkda joylashgan tishning pastgi qismi). [2]

Having studied the given versions in the dictionary and having compared them with the English dictionary of synonyms and an explanatory dictionary, we

get the following versions of translation: – tayanch.

The process of the semantic development suggests to be made in different stages:

- a) perception of the whole context;
- b) specification of the meaning of separate words;
- c) check on the conformity to the context;
- d) construction of the logical chains;
- e) a choice of a comprehensible variant;
- f) check of the words in the whole context.

Thus the logical reasoning plays a main role, taking into account the content of the initial text. Owing to the features of the language while translating from English into Uzbek the translator is compelled quite often to resort to a various sorts of substitution of separate words, word-combinations, parts of the sentences and translation of the whole sentence to express fully the content of the text being translated in a target language. Substitution happens when changing the word with another one and not changing the sense.

Different ways of substitution are defined, such as concretization, generalization, antonymous translation, compensation, extension of thought and perception as a whole. Some of them are applied in the translation of fashion terms. Necessity in applying the methods of the additions or omissions is often required by the norms of language. For example, the term Quadrants is translated as Четыречастъвашегорта in Russian. The term is translated by addition, because if we do it as it is given in English, not using the addition, there will be no sense. In Uzbek it will be as og`iz bo`shlig`ining to`rtta qisimi. The omission is also widely used as the addition. [3]

For example, *Deciduous teeth* – *sut tishi*. The word ballerina does not bear the most necessary sense, so it is not much important to translate it. The words sut can give its sense.

During the research we defined four tools of stomatology terms:

- transliteration;
- semantic equivalents;
- calque;
- description.

Transliteration is the practice of converting a text from one writing system into another in a semantic way, word by word, or ideally letter by letter. Transliteration attempts to use a one-to-one correspondence and be exact, so that an informed reader should be able to reconstruct the original spelling of unknown transliterated words. To achieve the objective, transliteration may define complex convention for dealing with letters in a source script which do not correspond the letters in a goal script. [4] For example, the words *dentin*, *plum*, *canal*, *cares*, *pulp*, *enamel*, *aspiration*, are transliterated into Uzbek as *дентин*, *пломба*, *канал*, *кариес*, *пульпа*, *эмаль*, *аспиратсия*.

The second tool of translation of the terms is the using of the semantic equivalents. Analogy is a cognitive process of transferring a word, word combination or phrase from a particular language to another particular one, and a linguistic expression corresponding to such a process. It is mostly used when the translator finds the Uzbek root corresponding to the meaning of the English term. For example, *gums –milk*, *denture – protez*, *cusped –so`yloq tish*, *labial– o`g`ri tish*, *erup –tishning tushishi* and so on. From the academic point of view these translations are most adequate, but it is not always possible to pick up full equivalents.

We would like to analyze some stomatology terms used in situations of three languages taken from the book.

Dentist recommend that you go for a check –up at least twice a year. At the same time as you see the dentist, you can also make an appointment with the dental hygienist who will clean and polish your teeth for you. The dentist checks that your teeth are in good condition. If you have a hole, or a cavity, you may

need a filling, which is a small amount of porcelain that the dentist uses to fill the hole.

Tish shifokorlari bir yilda kamida ikki marta, tish shifokori ko`rigidan o`tishni tavsiya qiladi. Agar siz tish shifokoriga uchrashmasangiz, tish gigienistiga uchrashib tishlaringizni ostki qismini tozalatishingiz mumkin. Tish shifokori, sizning tishlaringiz qay holatda ekanligini tekshiradi. Agar kovak yoki bo'shliq bo'lsa, shifokor kovak bo`lgan joyni yopish uchun maxsus yasama emal qorishmasidan, kerakli miqdorda foydalanib davolashi mumkin.

Starting with the phrase term go for a check- up. Uzbek version of it is ko`rikdan o`tish Though semantic equivalents of the words are given, the translator made an omission using one word o`tish for the translation of two words go and up. However, the Russian version is the shortest one, as there is an omission in two places. check- up is given with one word. The term cavity is translated adequately both in Russian and Uzbek languages, using the lexico-semantic translation. The semantic equivalents of the phrase term dental hygienist are given adequately in both languages.

Though the addition is used in Uzbek translation in the word porcelain - yasama (yaltirab turuvchi) emal. Unlike English or Russian versions, Uzbek translation is wrong translation in using the illnesses. The word cavity is given adequately in Russian - кариес where as Uzbek version is tish qurtlashi, but the English version of this word is cvity. The adequate translation is karies. According to the examples above we can subdivide the words into two groups: word-formation and semantic. Word-formation calques are the words received by morphemic translation of foreign words to Russian or Uzbek. The calques usually are not loan words, as they are made of primordially Russian or Uzbek morphemes.[5]

Therefore the real origin of such words seems unexpected for the person, learning etymology of words for the first time. Semantic calques are the words which have received new values under the influence of corresponding words of

another language as a result of transliteration while translating. If there is no other way to translate the terms, we can rely on the fourth tool of translation, so-called the descriptive translation. In most cases during the translation of terms related to stomatology the translator applies this tool, giving the meaning as shortly as he or she is able.

Let's see it in the examples such as numerical notation for teeth – численное обозначение для зубов – tishlarni sanoq sonlari yordamida atash or quadrants – четырехчастивашего рта – og`iz bo`shlig`ining to`rtta qismi. It is impossible to give the meaning by calc or analogy. The terms require descriptive translation, of course, we use some additions too.

Dentists training usually includes complicated oral surgery, root canal work, orthodontics (straightening teeth), and other complex skills. Yet most dentist rarely do more than pull, drill, and fill teeth – skills that require a fraction of the training they have received. The simple, more common dental problems should be the work of community dental technicians who are on the front lines (the villages), with secondary help from dentists for more difficult problems.

Tish shifokori mutaxassisligi asosan yuz jag` jarrohligini o`z ichiga oladi, tish ildizi kanallari, ortadontiya (tishlarni to`g`ri yo`naltirish) va yana shuningdek bir qancha murakkab ishlarni qamrab oladi. Biroq tish shifokorlari kutilgandan ko`ra ko`proq ish bajarishadi, masalan tishni davolash jarayonida uni maxsus drel yordamida tish kanalini ochish va kovakni tozalab uni yopish. Oddiy, ko`p uchraydigan muommolar umumiy tishning texnik muammolari bo`lib, ular asosan chekka joydagi qishloqlarda uchraydi, markazlashgan joylarda esa tish shifokorlari yanada murakkabroq muommolarga uchraydi.

Here we translated the text in the omission and admission way, the word straightening teeth- tishlarni to`g`ri yo`naltiruvchi in Russian version выпрямление зубов. The word drill translated adequately because this word translated in to Russian сверло or дрель in Uzbek version it translated parma yani metallarni maydaluvchi uskuna. This kind of terms are translated by

adequately or with analogy, with definition. It is impossible to give their own meaning. The terms require descriptive translation, of course, we use some additions too. The term oral surgery is also translated with admission way, in Uzbek language it will be yuz jag` - jarroxligi in Russian челюстно-лицевойхирургия, We add here the word in Uzbek yuz - jag` in Russian also the same. If we translate 48 just the word oral it will be another meaning, in to Uzbek it will be talafuz nuqtasi, in Russian относящихсякустью .[6]

The word root canal is translated in word for word translation way root – ildiz – корен, canal – kanal – канал. The word canal related to transliteration words because in this translation way words translated one by one or we say such kind of words does not change their meanings. So, not only an adequate version of giving the sense of the initial text are singled out as the main thing in the translation process, but also cognitive knowledge, logic, a context, ability to abstract concept at a synonym choice are available.

If the translation of the term already exists, it is necessary to choose it no matter what model is used. It is necessary to give the preference to the semantic equivalents, providing the adequate translation of a detail-logic sense of the term. In comparison with a transliteration, the way of translation allows the native speakers of any language to reach understanding of the translated term. In translation of the compound terms it is also necessary to choose elements from Uzbek, instead of the borrowed bases. As we analyzed the stomatology terms, we come to the conclusion that in most cases they are not translated, but are given by the way of transliteration/transcription, because the background of the terms is considered to be brought from Latin.

Used literature

1. Evans, V., et al. (2012). Career Path Medical. Express Publishing
2. Хўжаева Л.У., Зохидова Х.А., Рахматуллаева З.З. Лотин тили. – Тошкент, 2005. – С. 8.
3. Саидқодирова Д.С. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида интернет терминларининг лингвистик тадқиқи: филол. фан. бўйича фалсафа д-ри (PhD) дисс. – Тошкент, 2018. – Б.53.
4. Қосимова Ф.Х. Ўзбек тилшунослигида тиббий терминологиянинг тараққиёт тенденциялари. // НамДУ илмий ахборотномаси. 2020, –№ 3. – Б.413
5. Medical encyclopedic dictionary. -Tashkent: Encyclopedia, 1994.- 291
6. Величко О.В. Англо-французские заимствования в русской медицинской терминологии: Автореф.дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Астрахань, 2010. – С. 14.